

SPEAKING SKILL AND ITS IMPROVEMENT

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Abstract. *To provide pupils some methods to enhance their speaking skills.*

Key words: *Speaking success, small texts, new words and making sentences.*

РАЗГОВОРНЫЙ НАВЫК И ЕГО СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ

Аннотация. *Предоставить учащимся некоторые методы для улучшения их разговорных навыков.*

Ключевые слова: *успех в устной речи, небольшие тексты, новые слова и составление предложений.*

The field of education is very comprehensive, and the focus on teaching foreign languages is increasing year by year. Today, the requirement of a foreign language certificate when applying to universities has motivated students to study English, Uzbek, Turkish, German, French and other languages thoroughly.

When we talk about the English language, first of all, the teacher tries to use different methods to make it simple and understandable for young learners of this language. Unfortunately, the teaching method may not be suitable for all students.

While it is a good thing that our young students can quickly learn grammatical topics, we are saddened by the fact that their speech is very slow, and in some cases they cannot speak at all. In today's article, we will consider several methods for students to speak faster and more fluently.

Working with small texts.

We should never give new learners a large text and tell them to memorize it. The reason is that the reader finds it difficult and thinks that I can't do it. This in turn causes mental depression. Doesn't want to teach and most of the time comes to the conclusion that I should stop learning the language. In order to effectively deal with such situations, the teacher should give students an opportunity to memorize a small text in each lesson. For example, if the student's level is beginner, the following text will suit them:

My name is Nozima and I am 10 years old. I like to read books. My favorite pet is a cat. I play with it every day.

As you can see, the text is very simple and consists of only 4 or 5 sentences. It is in this way that we can keep students interested in the language.

Praise the learner.

Every person is individual and everyone's world is different. Some people learn faster, while others learn more slowly. In both cases, we should use the student and give him a compliment. It's important to say that instead of saying that you don't speak enough, say that word wrong, you didn't prepare well, I'm very happy, you're doing great, and I believe you can speak even better. Every student expects attention from the teacher. We must not forget that

Make sentences with new words.

Unfortunately, another mistake many teachers make is to tell students to memorize new words. A modern pedagogue explains how to use dictionaries and says that more attention should be paid to sentences than to words. It is wrong to give just words to learn, instead of it we should encourage pupils to make sentences. For example, if we have the word "BENEFICAL" we can say our people "Learning English is really beneficial" and then pupils will be aware of its meaning, structure.